

CALCULATIONS FOR THE INCREASING RADIUS AND MASS OF THE EARTH

The slowing rotation of the Earth is well established. What is not yet decided or confirmed is how much does the action of the ocean tides slow the Earth's rotation and what percentage is from other causes. Measured variations in the rate of the Earth's slowing rotation, particularly in the last 200 years, help to establish an allocation for the lost momentum that is not related to the tides. Figure 9.1, (Stephenson 1991) diagrams a rate of 1.37 *ms/cy* that is non-tidal. This rate is also supported by medieval Arab eclipse timings.

Fig. 9.1. Changes in the length of day (ΔLOD) relative to the reference day of 86400 SI seconds as derived from medieval Arab eclipse timings. The accurately mapped fluctuations since A.D. 1780 are shown for comparison. Also shown are the best fitting straight line to the data points which passes through $\Delta\text{LOD} = 0$ at A.D. 1800 (full line) and the theoretical tidal variation (broken line).

We will use the following data for our calculations:

Mean radius Earth	= r_0	= 6.371×10^6 meters
Mass of Earth	= m_0	= 5.9736×10^{24} kg
Moment of Inertia	= I	= $.3308mr^2$
Angular Velocity	= ω	= $131,490^0 / \text{yr}$ = $2294.933433 \text{ rad/yr}$
Change in velocity	= $\Delta\omega$	= $3.6361 \times 10^{-5} \text{ rad / yr}$ = $.50 \text{ sec/yr (time)}$ = 1.37 ms/cy

Angular Momentum $=L = I\omega$

$$L = (.3308m_0r_0^2)(\omega_0)$$

$$= .3308(5.9736 \times 10^{24})(6.371 \times 10^6)^2(2294.933433)$$

$$= 1.8407166 \times 10^{41}$$

To solve for the increase in mass and radius we put m in terms of r :

$$m = k \cdot \frac{4}{3}\pi r^3 \quad k = \text{density conversion constant for mass to radius}$$

$$k = \frac{5.9736 \times 10^{24}}{4/3\pi(6.371 \times 10^6)^3}$$

$$k = 5,514.73583405$$

Returning to our equation for angular momentum:

$$L = .3308r_0^2 \cdot 4/3k\pi r_0^3 \cdot \omega_0$$

$$L = 8/15k\pi r_0^5 \cdot \omega_0$$

We introduce another constant to reduce the numbers in the equation:

$$K = 8/15k\pi$$

$$K = 9.11954267 \times 10^4$$

Which yields:

$$L = K \cdot r^5 \omega \quad (9.1)$$

To find the rate of increase in the radius we differentiate:

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = K(5r^4\omega \frac{dr}{dt} + r^5 \frac{d\omega}{dt}) \quad (9.2)$$

If we hold to Newton's first law then L remains constant and $\frac{dL}{dt} = 0$

$$\text{Therefore:} \quad 5r^4\omega \frac{dr}{dt} = -r^5 \frac{d\omega}{dt} \quad (9.3)$$

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = \frac{-r}{5\omega} \frac{d\omega}{dt} \quad (9.4)$$

$$= \frac{-6.371 \times 10^6 (-3.6361 \times 10^{-5}) \text{ rad / yr}}{5(2294.933433)}$$

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = 2.01884663 \text{ cm / yr}$$

This deduction shows that the radius of the Earth is increasing at a current rate of approximately 2 centimeters per year.

The next task is to solve for the increase in mass. If density is to remain constant then the mass of the Earth is increasing with the cube of the radius. The following equation yields the increase in the mass of the Earth for one year:

$$\begin{aligned}
 m &= k \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \\
 \frac{dm}{dt} &= k \frac{4}{3} \pi 3r^2 \frac{dr}{dt} && (9.5) \\
 &= k 4\pi r^2 \frac{dr}{dt} \\
 &= 5,514.73583405 \cdot 4\pi \cdot (6.371 \times 10^6)^2 \cdot .0202 \\
 &= 5.68523302 \times 10^{16} \text{ kg / yr}
 \end{aligned}$$

To check if our calculations are correct, we insert $m + \Delta m, r + \Delta r, \text{ and } \omega - \Delta \omega$ into our equation for angular momentum. According to Newton's first law, L should not change.

$$\begin{aligned}
 L &= .3308 \cdot 5.97360006 \times 10^{24} \cdot 6,371,000.0202^2 \cdot 2294.93339664 \\
 L &= 1.84071666 \times 10^{41}
 \end{aligned}$$

This result is equal to our original calculation for angular momentum indicating that it is conserved.

This analysis shows what the increase in radius and mass of the Earth would be if there exists an inherent dynamic nature to matter. It thus provides us a mechanism that may account for the anomalous momentum problem regarding the Earth's rotation. Tidal friction and geophysical solutions seem to fall short of solving this anomaly. In addition, the results from this analysis can be extended to the anomalous momentum problems regarding the Moon's increasing orbit, the slowing Pioneer spacecraft and the rotating galaxies. The predicted change in the Earth's mass:

$$5.68 \times 10^{16} \text{ kg / year}$$

is used as the rate of increase in the analysis of these other anomalies. If we take our Δm and divide it by the mass of the Earth, we then have the universal decimal percentage rate for which mass is increasing. This rate for one year is:

$$\frac{\Delta m / m}{\Delta t} = 9.5119 \times 10^{-9} / \text{year}$$

This number can be considered a constant and assigned the symbol: m_d

Converting this rate of change to seconds we have:

$$m_d = 3.0142 \times 10^{-16} / \text{sec}$$

Applying the same conversion for decimal percentage rate of change for any given radius, we have:

$$r_d = 1.0047 \times 10^{-16} / \text{sec}$$

We can also do the same for ω , and the decimal percentage rate of change for rotational velocity for any given rotating body is:

$$\omega_d = -5.0235 \times 10^{-16} / \text{sec}$$

We will see throughout the remainder of this study how these three values can be applied to various anomalies and produce results that are very close to what is observed.

DERIVING EQUIVALENCE OF MASS TO SPACE

With the view that space is flowing rather than warping, the velocity of the inward flow of space was derived in Section 7. By using Einstein's formula for calculating the curvature of light as it passes by a body of mass, the average value of 19.75 meters/second was attained. Using the area of the surface of the Earth and the amount of space that passes inward in one second, one can derive the volume of space that is consumed in one second. The amount of mass the Earth is gaining in one year was calculated in the previous section and the value of $5.6852 \times 10^{16} \text{ kg / yr}$ was attained. Converting this number to attain the gain in mass per second and taking the ratio of this number with volume of space consumed will give us an estimate of the equivalence factor of space to mass.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Surface area of the Earth:} \quad a &= 4\pi r^2 \\
 &= 4\pi(6.38 \times 10^6)^2 \\
 a &= 5.11506 \times 10^{14} \text{ m}^2 \\
 \text{Volume of space per second:} \quad \text{vol/sec} &= a \cdot 19.75 \text{ m / sec} \\
 &= 5.11506 \times 10^{14} \cdot 19.75 \\
 \text{vol/sec} &= 1.0102 \times 10^{16} \text{ m}^3 / \text{sec} \\
 \text{Gain in mass/year:} \quad \Delta m / \Delta t &= 5.6852 \times 10^{16} \text{ kg / yr} \\
 \text{Gain in mass/sec:} \quad \Delta m / \Delta t &= 1.8016 \times 10^9 \text{ kg / sec} \\
 \frac{\text{vol / sec}}{\text{mass / sec}} : \quad m^3 / \text{kg} &= \frac{1.0102 \times 10^{16}}{1.8016 \times 10^9} \\
 &= 5,607,150 \text{ m}^3 / \text{kg}
 \end{aligned}$$

Approximately 5,607,000 cubic meters of space is equal to one kilogram of mass.

This volume of space is being drawn in and converted to mass per second each second, therefore our number becomes:

$$5.607 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 / \text{kg} / \text{sec}^2$$

This relationship demonstrates the proportionality of space to mass.

Returning to our previous deduction for the volume of space per kilogram, we arrived at 5,607,000 cubic meters per kilogram each second. We can insert this conversion value into the equation derived from Newton's law of gravity and establish an equality of space to mass:

$$space = 5.607 \times 10^6 mt^2 \quad (10.1)$$

There are features of this equation that may be of significance. Our conversion constant was derived from theory and can be supported through measurement. In addition, the dimensions of our conversion constant; $meters^3 / kg / sec^2$, are also naturally derived and provide the dimensional conversion necessary to establish the equality of space to mass. We have thus defined a new constant: a constant that defines the conversion of space to mass for each passing second of time. For convenience I have assigned it the symbol "DM." Our equation can now be written as:

$$space = DM \cdot mt^2 \quad (10.2)$$

$$\text{with } DM = 5.607 \times 10^6 \text{ meters}^3 / kg / sec^2$$